

**BILINGUISM IS A TERM REPRESENTING
CONCEPTS OF LANGUAGE RELATIONSHIPS**
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Annotation: In this article, the history of the emergence of bilingualism, the importance of bilingualism in world linguistics, the views of linguists in this regard, and its contribution to intercultural relations are studied and analyzed.

Key words: bilingualism, bilinguals, issues of bilingualism, intercultural communication, dialectal and international interface.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that one of the terms expressing the concepts of language relations is bilingualism. Bilingualism (bilingualism) means to communicate freely in two languages, to be bilingual. People who engage in mutual communication in two languages are considered to be bilingual. If we focus on the origin of this term, the Romans conquered Iberia (modern Spain) and Gaul (modern France) in the III-II centuries BC. Bilingualism of the local language - Latin is emerging in these regions.

Bilingualism is a Latin word, "bi" means two, and "lingua" means language, that is, bilingualism.

As a term, bilingual means a person who has the ability to speak two languages in everyday life: his mother tongue and one foreign language. Today, we see that people are learning two or three languages at the same time. So, can we call them all bilingual?

So, bilinguals are people who know and can speak a second language as well as their mother tongue.

Types of bilingualism

People who have been able to communicate easily in two languages since childhood are also called bilinguals, in fact, this term expresses bilingualism formed as a result of living in a bilingual environment. For this reason, first of all, we divide bilingualism into artificial and natural forms.

1. In artificial bilingualism, at a certain stage of a person's life, a second language is added and acquired just like a mother tongue.

2. A natural bilingual learns two languages from an early age.

It should be mentioned that the concept of bilingualism formed under the influence of the environment is also divided into two:

1. Individual bilinguals are people who grew up with bilingualism based on family circumstances or personal desire.

2. Social bilinguals are people who have mastered two languages at the same time under the influence of the current situation or traditions in the country.

Individual bilinguals acquire both languages equally as a result of growing up in a family where their parents speak two different languages. It is not necessary for the parents to be of two nationalities. People who know a foreign language perfectly can easily raise their children bilingually.

Social bilingualism is formed in societies where there is more than one state language in the country, historically a colony or vassal of a state. Basically, this situation is observed more among European countries. For example, in Switzerland, there are 4 official national languages, and in such conditions, people master at least two languages equally.

Bilingualism is further divided into 3 types according to the degree to which a person masters two languages:

1. Coordinative or balanced bilingualism. In this case, a person learns two languages in a separate context. In the brains of such people, a separate vocabulary for both languages, separate grammatical concepts are formed. The concepts of the two languages do not get mixed up when speaking.

2. Sub-coordinative or unbalanced bilingualism. In this case, the first language has priority over the second. That is, the second language is acquired through the mother tongue. For example, when hearing a word in a second language, the equivalent of that word in the mother tongue immediately comes to mind.

3. Mixed bilingualism. Such bilinguals can understand and support two languages in the same context. The brain of such people does not care about the language they are using. Mixed bilingualism usually develops in the family during infancy due to bilingual parents.

As a result of the in-depth study of bilingualism and the Russian language, issues such as the improvement of Turkish literary languages and the enrichment of stylistic features in them, in particular, the use of new rhythm and metric in the poetic style, the activation of new poetic forms and classical poetic laws, will be opened more widely: - I went to Balbestg's house. I talked to the old woman. I started a criminal case, and I'm sorry. After all, the wedding in a month! Da, mejdu prochem, do' will transfer the house to the name of Balbestng until the wedding. If he doesn't, his son will rot in prison. (Z. p. 114)

The fact that the Uzbek and Tajik peoples have been living side by side in the same area for centuries has also had an impact on the lexical-semantic structure of these languages. As a result, Uzbek-Tajik bilingualism was born. It should be noted that the lexical-semantic influence is not as obvious as the phonetic influence, even if it is widespread. Therefore, the main attention of the researchers was focused on the phonetic effect, and the interlingual lexical-semantic effect was neglected. Since the Uzbek and Tajik languages are bilingual, "...the language of the Tajiks living in the regions of Bukhara, Samarkand, Fergana Valley has similarities and typological closeness with the Uzbek language at various linguistic levels." In the northern dialects of the Tajik language, the phrase "felro ovardan" is used in the sense of "to take out the bitterness", "to take out the anger". In this example, the Tajik and Uzbek models have been combined to form "to extract the verb". If we look at the example of the work of the writer Tahir Malik: "The guest watched his actions. Although he

was bitter at his rudeness, he did not lose the secret and looked at the host" He did a lot of things that made him angry and made him angry (Sh. IV, vol. 86-b).

Current contacts of the Uzbek language with related and non-related languages, bilingualism and related phenomena are one of the most important current problems facing Uzbek linguists. In Uzbek linguistics, there are no special theoretical works devoted to language relations and their influence on each other. This motivates the work related to the concept of bilingualism and interference in the field of language. There is also a collection of articles devoted to the various problems of bilingualism and multilingualism, which cover issues such as bilingualism, its types, historical roots, language interference, its essence, and attitudes to bilingualism.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the Uzbek language has wide possibilities and the role of bilingualism in it is incomparable. Bilingualism also greatly contributes to the development of communication and communication between cultures. We have examined the proof of this above in the example of Tahir Malik's works. It is desirable to study the issues of bilingualism both theoretically and practically in the next stages of linguistics.

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